

The Role of Structural Supervision as a Mediator on the Resource Management Ability of School Principals' and Teachers' Cooperation

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Abstract. The main purpose of this study was to evaluate whether structural supervision significantly mediates the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation. In this study, the researcher selected 200 public elementary school teachers in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte as the respondents of the survey. A stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation, and Sobel z-Test. Descriptive analysis showed that the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation were described as extensive, while structural supervision of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte was rated moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there was a significant relationship between the resource management ability of school principals, teachers' cooperation, and structural supervision of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. Evidently, Sobel z-Test proved that structural supervision significantly mediates the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte.

KEY WORDS

1. educational management 2. resource management ability of school principals 3. teachers' cooperation 4. structural supervision

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1. Introduction

Structural supervision acts as a critical moderating variable that enhances and facilitates the positive impact of effective resource management on teachers' cooperation. For instance, structural supervision involves clearly defining teacher expectations regarding resource utilization and cooperative behavior. This provides a structured framework for teachers to understand their roles and responsibilities. Structural supervision often includes protocols and mechanisms for resolving conflicts among teachers or between teachers and the administration. This is crucial because conflicts can disrupt cooperation. Resolving conflicts promptly and fairly can help maintain a harmonious working environment. More so, structural supervision serves

as a crucial bridge between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation. It establishes the necessary structure, expectations, support, and accountability mechanisms that maximize the positive impact of resource management on cooperation. When these components are well-integrated, they create a conducive environment for teachers to work collaboratively and efficiently, ultimately contributing to the school's success and students' educational experience. Meanwhile, Heissenberger and Heilbronner (2011) highlighted that the resource management ability of a school principal plays a pivotal role in fostering teachers' cooperation. Structural supervision complements this by providing the necessary structure, accountability, and support to maximize the positive impact of resource management on teacher collaboration. When these elements work in tandem, they can create a conducive environment for enhanced cooperation and the school's overall success. More so, Ambali et al. (2011) reported that principals adept at resource management can allocate resources effectively. This includes budgetary resources for instructional materials, professional development, support staff, and physical resources like classrooms and technology. They can provide teachers with opportunities for professional development, workshops, and training, which enhances their teaching skills and motivation. As viewed by Sergiovanni (2013), structural supervision holds school principals accountable for their administrative and leadership roles. It ensures that they are fulfilling their duties and responsibilities. Barber et al. (2010) added that structural supervision promotes a moderate consistency in how different principals are evaluated, reducing the likelihood of subjective judgments. There is a moderate level of standardization in the assessment and monitoring process, with predefined criteria and performance expectations. Likewise, Day et al. (2011) noted that structural supervision holds school principals accountable for their leadership and administrative roles, ensuring they meet the established standards and expectations. It serves as a quality assurance mechanism to maintain and enhance the quality of education in schools. As described by Demo et al. (2012), resource management ability is the principal's capacity to effectively oversee and allocate various resources within the educational institution to support its mission and educational goals. According to Dessler (2013), principals with high resource management ability can allocate resources strategically to support the school's educational objectives and improve overall school performance. They use data and evidence-based practices to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation, ensuring that resources are directed where they will have the most impact. Choudhary and Lamba (2013) noted that principals with resource management abilities actively engage with teachers, staff, and other stakeholders in collaborative resource management, involving them in decision-making to optimize resources collectively. They demonstrate advanced conflict resolution skills to address complex resource-related disputes and concerns constructively and collaboratively. According to Oswald (2014), teachers who cooperate at a high level can collaboratively plan lessons and teaching strategies, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards and optimizing student learning experience. High levels of cooperation facilitate shared professional development opportunities. Teachers can learn from one another and build on each other's expertise. Khattri et al. (2010) asserted that cooperation supports a culture of continuous improvement. Teachers engage in reflective practices and adapt their teaching methods based on feedback and results. Teachers cooperate to share responsibility for achieving educational goals and ensuring students meet academic standards. Likewise, Lindgerg and Vanyushyn (2013) noted that a cooperative environment fosters a posi-

tive school culture where teachers feel valued and supported, contributing to higher morale and job satisfaction. It is noted that there are shortcomings in the cooperation of some public elementary school teachers worldwide. For instance, Charmaz's (2014) lack of cooperation among teachers resulted in a decline in the overall quality of education, affecting student learning outcomes and potentially causing dissatisfaction among parents and stakeholders. Without cooperation, students may not receive the necessary support and fall through the cracks. Also, Kangasnieumi et al. (2016) noted that lack of cooperation contributes to a hostile school culture where teachers may become disengaged, cynical, or resistant to change. This can affect the overall morale of the school community. According to Dufour et al. (2016), teachers who do not collaborate may feel isolated, leading to increased stress and burnout. Sharing ideas and resources with colleagues can provide emotional support and alleviate the pressures of teaching. Despite the growing recognition of the crucial roles played by school principals in effective resource management and the promotion of teachers' cooperation, there is a notable gap in the existing literature regarding the mediating role of structural supervision. While studies have explored the direct impact of resource management ability on teachers' cooperation, there is a limited understanding of how structural supervision may mediate or enhance this relationship. This research gap highlights the need for a comprehensive investigation into the intricate dynamics between school principals' resource management ability, the structural supervision practices they employ, and the resulting impact on teachers' cooperation, providing valuable insights for educational leaders and policy-makers seeking to improve collaboration and educational outcomes within schools. Thus, in this context, the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap by conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Talaingod

District, Davao del Norte, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made use of structural equation modeling through mediation analysis to have a better understanding of the teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte, as determined by the resource management ability of the school principal and mediated by structural supervision, which is found to be scarce.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. Resource Management Ability—

Demo et al. (2012) describe resource management ability as the principal's capacity to effectively oversee and allocate resources within the educational institution. Dessler (2013) notes that principals with high resource management ability can strategically allocate resources to support educational objectives, using data and evidence-based practices. Gould-Sandy (2013) emphasizes strategic planning to align resource allocation with the school's mission. Ellinger (2016) adds that high resource management promotes transparency and accountability, with principals optimizing resources and engaging stakeholders collaboratively. Tiwari and Saxena (2012) and Choudhary and Lamba (2013) highlight the importance of continuous monitoring and innovative strategies for resource efficiency.

Marler and Boudreau (2017) and Armstrong and Taylor (2014) underline prioritizing resource allocation for programs benefiting students' development, involving stakeholders in resource management discussions. Armstrong and Brown (2019) and Shaukat et al. (2015) link effective resource management to academic excellence and financial health. Gerhart (2015) focuses on managing human resources, impacting student achievement. Tabouli et al. (2016) and Lim (2012) discuss the alignment of HRM policies with business strategy. Olesia et al. (2013) and Almutairi (2020) find a correlation between workforce management and subordinates' ethical behavior, engagement, and performance.

Ambali et al. (2011) and Boey (2010) con-

nect workforce management to employee ethical behavior and organizational involvement. Fitzgerald (2020) asserts that good corporate ethics enhance loyalty and commitment. Francisco and Claro (2017) find that positive workforce management influences ethical behavior and job satisfaction.

1.1.2. Workforce Management—Demo et al. (2012) and Hilaire and Kosinski (2015) describe workforce management as the principal's capacity to oversee and allocate human resources, ensuring productive work environments. Hubschmid (2013) and Bogatova (2017) note that moderate workforce management supports staff development and satisfaction.

1.1.3. Collaboration—Demo et al. (2012) and Liphadzi et al. (2015) emphasize the principal's role in engaging stakeholders to optimize resources. Angelle and Teague (2014) and Mukeshimana (2016) discuss the importance of fostering teamwork and involving staff in decision-making processes.

1.1.4. Professional Development—Demo et al. (2012) and Kumar (2013) highlight the significance of continuous learning for effective resource management. Baker (2015) and Schleicher (2021) emphasize strategic planning and resource optimization. Joynes et al. (2019) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) underscore the role of professional development in achieving higher student outcomes.

1.1.5. School Climate—Demo et al. (2012) and Selamat et al. (2013) describe school climate as the atmosphere and social environment within the school, affecting resource management. Sherman (2018) and Vijayabanu (2017) link positive school climate to collaborative resource management and increased community support. Boudreaux Martin and McNeal (2016) and Lumpkin (2013) note that good facilities improve teacher performance and engagement.

1.1.6. Competency-Based Performance Appraisal—Demo et al. (2012) and Valentine

et al. (2014) discuss competency-based performance appraisal as assessing principals' skills in resource management. Herlambang (2013) and Febriyanto (2012) emphasize transparency and accountability in resource allocation.

1.1.7. Compensation and Rewards—Demo et al. (2012) and Chege (2016) highlight the importance of financial remuneration for teachers' motivation. Kossivi et al. (2016) and Monaco (2016) discuss the long-term impacts of benefits and incentives on job satisfaction and retention.

1.1.8. Teachers' Cooperation—Abdulla Al Kaabi (2015) and Oswald (2014) define teachers' cooperation as the commitment to work collaboratively to achieve educational goals. Barrera-Osorio et al. (2010) and Khattri et al. (2010) link cooperation to comprehensive student support and continuous improvement. Cheng and Mok (2010) and Moos (2010) emphasize the role of mentoring and community involvement in fostering a cooperative environment. Vernez Karam and Marshall (2012) and Moradi et al. (2012) stress the impact of school-based management on teacher morale and commitment.

1.1.9. Leadership and Governance—The role of school leadership in fostering collaboration and cooperation among teachers, involving strategies and policies to promote a culture of teamwork.

1.2. Synthesis—Studies on structural supervision, resource management ability of school principals, and teachers' cooperation underscores the intricate relationship between these elements in the educational landscape. It highlights the need for further research to delve deeper into the mechanisms and factors that can enhance or impede cooperation, as well as the potential impacts on student success. Multiple studies emphasize the critical role of school principals in resource management. Effective allocation of resources, such as finances, time, and personnel, contributes to the

overall functioning of a school. Research consistently shows that proper resource management by school principals positively influences teachers' cooperation. Educational leaders should consider the insights provided by this synthesis to improve the quality of education and the overall school environment.

1.3. Theoretical Conceptual Framework— The study was anchored on Heissenberger and Heilbronner's (2011) proposition that the resource management ability of a school principal plays a pivotal role in fostering teachers' cooperation. Structural supervision complements this by providing the necessary structure, accountability, and support to maximize the positive impact of resource management on teacher collaboration. When these elements work in tandem, they can create a conducive environment for enhanced cooperation and the overall success of the school. According to Oumer and Kejela (2017), effective structural supervision can enhance the impact of resource management by ensuring that the resources allocated are used efficiently. It can also ensure that teachers are accountable for their use of resources. In support, Ambali et al. (2011) postulated that principals who are adept at resource management can allocate resources effectively. This includes budgetary resources for instructional materials, professional development, support staff, and physical resources like classrooms and technology. They can provide teachers with opportunities for professional development, workshops, and training, which enhances their teaching skills and motivation. As shown in Figure 1, the study is consisting of two variables. The study's independent variable is resource management ability or principal's capacity to effectively oversee and allocate various resources within the educational institution to support its mission and educational goals. According to Demo et al. (2012) resource management strategies was measured in terms of workforce management or school principal's capacity to effectively over-

see and allocate human resources within the educational institution; collaboration or the extent to which the principal actively engages with various stakeholders, both within and outside the school, to collectively manage and allocate resources effectively; professional development or the continuous learning, training, and skill enhancement activities undertaken by the principal to improve their competencies in managing and optimizing resources within the educational institution; school climate or the prevailing atmosphere, culture, and social environment within the school; competency-based performance appraisal or the assessment process that evaluates the principal's proficiency in key competencies and skills related to resource management within an educational institution; and compensation and rewards or the organization's ability to reward employees' performance and competence via remuneration and incentives. The study's dependent variable was described as teachers' cooperation or the approach or willingness, ability, and commitment of teachers to work collaboratively with their colleagues, school administrators, and other stakeholders within the educational institution. According to DepEd (2012), the measures of teachers' cooperation are leadership and governance, or the role of school leadership and the administrative framework in fostering and promoting a culture of collaboration and cooperation among teachers; curriculum and instruction or the role of the educational curriculum and instructional strategies in promoting and facilitating a culture of collaboration among teachers; accountability and continuous improvement or the establishment of a system of accountability and continuous improvement processes that promote and enhance a culture of collaboration and cooperation among teachers; and management of resources or the strategic allocation, utilization, and facilitation of resources within an educational institution to support and enhance a culture of collaboration and cooperation among teachers. The

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

mediating variable was structural supervision systematically monitored and assessed based on the supervisory approach in which the performance and activities of school principals are on predefined criteria, guidelines, and organizational structures (Beverlin, 2011).

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary aim of this study was to determine the mediating effect of structural supervision on the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers’ cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of the resource management ability of school principal in terms of:
 - (1) workforce management;
 - (2) collaboration;
 - (3) professional development;
 - (4) school climate;
 - (5) competency-based performance appraisal;
 - (6) compensation and rewards?
- (2) What is the extent of teachers’ cooperation in terms of:
 - (1) leadership and governance;
 - (2) curriculum and instruction;
 - (3) accountability and continuous improvement; and
 - (4) resources management?
- (3) What is the extent of structural supervision of school principals in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte?

- (4) Is there a significant relationship between structural supervision, the resource management ability of the school principal, and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte?
- (5) Does structural supervision significantly mediate the relationship between school principals' resource management ability and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte?

1.5. Hypothesis—The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance: H01: There is no significant relationship between structural supervision, resource management ability of school principals, and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. H02: Structural supervision does not significantly mediate the relationship between the resource management ability of the school principals and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. Department of Education. The Department of Education would benefit because establishing the significant influence of these variables may provide a framework that aims to develop cooperation among elementary school teachers; the researcher believes that if the current situation is not urgently addressed, it may increase the risks of losing teachers' cooperation that may sooner or later paralyze the compromise their work status. Department of Education. This study would benefit policymakers since the findings may bridge the methodological divide in teaching practices research by attempting to understand not only the teachers' cooperation but also the aspect of resource management strategies of the school head. Hence, this study provides a synthesis of both approaches. In addition, while research on the effects of resource management strategies of school heads on teachers' cooperation has to date primarily focused on the tertiary education context, this program of research builds on the established relationship between resource management strategies of the school heads and teachers' cooperation in the elementary education context. Teachers. The result would benefit the teachers since the results generate facts, which is essential in providing administrative support to the teachers. Since it was already known that teachers' cooperation has a significant effect on the teachers' performance and was also an essential component of educational and instructional processes, the findings of this study would justify the importance of implementing positive resource management strategies for teachers' cooperation in work. Therefore, the evidence gathered from this study would be helpful for the teachers to develop working behavior that would consider their identity as professional teachers. Stakeholders. The study's findings were important because they provide facts that may enable stakeholders to evaluate their school programs and establish result-oriented procedures to help teachers and students who do not perform well achieve optimum productivity and quality learning outcomes. This may provide relevant information on the effects and effectiveness of teaching and learning activities on learners' performance and stimulate them to find realistic solutions to quality problems in education so that academic norms are not undermined at the expense of social norms but complement each other. Future researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the results of this study because the findings may provide a framework and model for future research on teachers' cooperation and school principals' resource management abilities. Also, the findings of this study would be baseline data for future studies and may contribute to the scarcity of quantitative studies on the relationship of these variables. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally:

Structural Supervision. This study refers to the mediating variable being expected to contribute to the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Resource Management Ability. This study refers to the independent variable described in terms of workforce management, collaboration, professional development, school climate, competency-based per-

formance appraisal, and compensation and rewards. Teachers' cooperation. This study refers to the dependent variable being described in terms of the following indicators: leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and resources management.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. We will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher utilized quantitative mediation analysis to gather data ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach where the emphasis was placed on the testing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while non-experimental research was research that lacked the manipulation of an independent variable. Meanwhile, mediation analysis was a statistical method used to quantify the causal sequence by which an antecedent variable causes a mediating variable that causes a dependent variable (Mackinnon, 2019). Specifically, the study focused on determining the mediating effect of structural supervision on the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation. Mediation analysis defines the direct, indirect, and total effects in

terms of the linear regression coefficients. The total effect was defined and estimated as the c coefficient and the direct effect was defined and estimated as the c' coefficient. The indirect effect is defined and estimated as the product of the a and b coefficients (ab) and as the difference between the c coefficient and the c' coefficient. The researcher used mediation analysis in this study because it provides information about how an independent variable affects a dependent variable.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study's respondents were elementary school teachers in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. In this study, the 200 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. According to Shi (2015), in stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or char-

acteristics, such as income or educational attainment. Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were implemented to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. The following are the inclusion criteria: currently employed teachers actively working within a school setting, teachers who have regular interactions with their school principal, teachers who are proficient in the English language, and those who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaire. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not consider the gender and socio-

economic status of the teachers.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first tool is about the resource management ability of the school principal. This questionnaire was adapted from Demo et al. (2012), which has six indicators: workforce management, collaboration, professional development, school climate, competence-based performance appraisal, and compensation and reward. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.928, which is interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. The instrument made use of a 5-point Likert scale that was determined based on the following range of mean:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The resource management ability of the school principal is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The resource management ability of school principals is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The resource management ability of the school principal is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The resource management ability of the school principal is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The resource management ability of the school principal is never manifested.

The second part was about teachers’ cooperation, adapted from the DepEd Revised School-Based Management Assessment Tool. The questionnaire comprises items indicated with leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management and resources. The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.930, which is interpreted as

excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. More so, this questionnaire was subjected to content validity by a panel of experts to test its validity. As a guide in determining the extent of teachers’ cooperation, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	Teachers' cooperation is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Teachers' cooperation is often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teachers' cooperation is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Teachers' cooperation is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Teachers' cooperation is never manifested.

The third part was about the structural supervision of school principals, which was adapted from the study of Beverlin (2011). The reliability of the new scale obtained Cronbach's alpha value of 0.955, which is interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. More so, this questionnaire

was subjected to content validity by a panel of experts to test its validity. As a guide in determining the extent of structural management of school principals, the researcher made use of the range of means, descriptions, and interpretations as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The structural supervision of the school principal is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The structural supervision of school principals is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The structural supervision of the school principal is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The structural supervision of the school principal is seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The structural supervision of the school principal is never evident.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher underwent steps in conducting the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school's division superintendent and then to the school principals of the selected elementary public schools in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher distributed the research instrument to the respondents after

the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last October 3-5, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the questionnaire administration, the researcher distributed the questionnaires following health protocols. The study respondents were given enough testing time to finish the questionnaires. After this, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the questionnaire was retrieved, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After that,

each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. *Informed Consent.* The researcher obtained the consent of respondents through written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study, and ample explanations were provided to help them better understand the reason for their participation so that they could choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study was voluntary. If they refused to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious in ensuring the respondents' psychological well-being. Written permission was secured from the respondents. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the teachers' cooperation concerning the resource management ability of school principals as mediated by structural supervision and may contribute to the enhancement. *Vulnerability of Research Participants.* The study's respondents are teachers, so they were not considered vulnerable since all of them are of legal age, and they were not considered highly vulnerable psychologically. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. *Privacy and Confidentiality.* This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012, wherein the researcher assured that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the natural source

of information, to protect the respondents' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the participants. Thus, the access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the survey information. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently deleted all the survey results to ensure that data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the real source of information. *Risk, Benefits, and Safety* - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study and the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the survey questionnaire. Without restrictions, the respondents could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not subjected to harm in any way whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the study's respondents. Likewise, this study was designed purely to collect academic information related to the study, and they were not asked for personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher ensured that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given the freedom not to answer questions that made them feel any psychological or emotional distress, and they would be free to withdraw as respondents to the study if they felt that they could not discuss the information that was being asked of them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the study. *Justice.* To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equally regardless of whether

they would be respondents in the survey. The researcher was not prejudiced in choosing the respondents for the study—anybody who fits the qualifications of being permanent-regular in the purposively selected schools. During the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenirs. The tokens were sent via courier, sealed carefully in a package. Also, each token was sanitized before being sent to your doorstep. Transparency. To provide transparency in this study, any communication related to the research was done with honesty and transparency. To safeguard the respondents' welfare, the researcher correctly implemented the methods discussed in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis were included. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that the respondents' responses were not influenced by other factors like the conflict of interest. The study's findings could be accessed by the respondent's parents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study; the Division of Davao del Norte was furnished with a copy of the research results so that the respondents could access them and use them for learning and further study. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials that were ample and available during the study, which was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gath-

ering data from the respondents was ensured by properly encoding the respondents' ratings during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results were proficient and aligned, serving as a primary basis for adequacy. Community Involvement. It was a good practice to have community involvement during every research phase, from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community and community involvement was accorded primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate methods to apply in their context, and the use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the structural supervision, resource management ability of the school principal, and teachers' cooperation. It was used to supply the answer for objectives 1, 2, and 3. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. It was used in this study to assess the significant relationship between independent (resource management ability of school principal), dependent (teachers' cooperation), and mediator (structural supervision) variables. It was a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. In a sample, it was usually denoted by r . This was used to supply the answer for objective 4. Sobel z -Test. It was applied to evaluate the significance of the mediator's (structural supervision) mediating effect on the relationship between the independent (resource management ability of school principal) and dependent (teachers' cooperation) variables. This was used to supply the answer for objective 5.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extent of the resource management ability of school principals, teachers’ cooperation, and structural supervision in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte; the significant relationship among resource management ability of school principals, teachers’ cooperation, and structural supervision in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte; and the mediating effect of structural supervision on the relationship between resource management ability of school principals and teachers’ cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte.

3.1. Resource Management Ability of School Principal In terms of Workforce Management—Table 1 shows an extensive category mean rating of 2.96, which means that the teachers in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte, sometimes observe this domain of resource management ability of school principals. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 1.84 to 3.42. The item, the school principal, has competitive selection processes that attract competent people and reflects a mean rating of 1.84, which is described as less extensive and interpreted as an item seldom observed. Meanwhile, the item, The school principal uses various selection instruments, shows a rating of 3.42, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes observed among school principals. This suggests that the school principal’s capacity to oversee and allocate human resources within the educational institution effectively is sometimes observed in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. This supports the view of Hilaire and Kosinski (2015) that a school principal with moderate workforce management skills can allocate human resources reasonably effectively, ensuring that staffing needs are met and tasks are delegated appropriately. This also supports the view of Hubschmid (2013) that at a moderate level, the principal supports staff development by providing some training opportunities and facilitating career growth but may not fully harness the potential of all team members.

Table 1. Resource Management Ability of School Principal in Terms of Workforce Management

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	The school principal widely disseminates information about both external and internal recruitment processes.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
2	The school principal discloses information to applicants regarding the steps and criteria of the selection process.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
3	Selection tests are conducted by trained and impartial people.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
4	The school principal has competitive selection processes that attract competent people.	1.84	Less Extensive
5	The school principal uses various selection instruments.	3.42	Extensive
Overall Mean		2.96	Moderately Extensive

3.2. Collaboration—Table 2 shows that the domain involvement was assessed by the teachers as moderately extensive with a category mean of 3.31, interpreted as sometimes

observed by the teachers in Talingod District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.78 to 3.72. On the one hand, the item The school head treats me with respect and attention has a mean rating of 2.78, described as moderately extensive and in-

terpreted as an item sometimes observed. On the other hand, the item Teachers and other staff enjoy the constant exchange of information in order to perform their duties properly reflects a mean of 3.77, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed.

Table 2. Resource Management Ability of School Principal in Terms of Collaboration

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	The school head treats me with respect and attention.	2.78	Moderately Extensive
2	The school head is concerned with my well-being.	3.04	Moderately Extensive
3	The school head recognizes the work I do and the results I achieve.	3.31	Moderately Extensive
4	The school head seeks to meet my needs and professional expectations.	3.68	Extensive
5	Teachers and other staff enjoy constant exchange of information in order to perform their duties properly.	3.72	Extensive
Mean		3.31	Moderately Extensive

This implies that the extent to which the principal actively engages with various stakeholders, both within and outside the school, to collectively manage and allocate resources effectively is sometimes observed in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The result is in line with the view of Angelle and Teague (2014) that principals can engage parents in resource-related discussions and decision-making, leading to reasonable levels of parental involvement in school matters. They may encourage resource sharing among teachers and departments, resulting in moderate resource optimization. This also supports the idea of Liphadzi et al. (2015) that a school principal with moderate collaboration skills can facilitate communication among stakeholders, ensuring that relevant information is shared and understood.

3.3. *Professional Development*—Specifically, examining the domain of professional development, results in Table 3 reveal that its category mean is 3.46, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain on resource management ability of school principals is oftentimes observed by the teachers in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.33 to 3.67. It is noteworthy that item, using knowledge and behaviors learned in training at work, has a mean rating of 3.33, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item is sometimes observed while item, the school head invests in my development and education promoting my personal and professional growth broadly has a mean rating of 3.67, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes observed in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte.

This implies that the continuous learning, training, and skill enhancement activities undertaken by the principal to improve their competencies in managing and optimizing resources

within the educational institution are oftentimes observed in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The result agrees with the view of Kumar (2013) that principals with high levels of professional

Table 3. Resource Management Ability of School Principal in Terms of Professional Development

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Using knowledge and behaviors learned in training at work.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
2	The school head helps me develop the skills I need for the successful accomplishment of my duties.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
3	The school head invests in my development and education, promoting my personal and professional growth in a broad manner.	3.67	Extensive
4	In the school, training is evaluated by participants.	3.51	Extensive
5	The school head stimulates learning and application of knowledge.	3.43	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.46	Extensive

development in resource management can effectively allocate financial and human resources to support the school’s educational objectives. They utilize data and evidence-based practices to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation and management, maximizing the impact of available resources. This also supports the view of Schleicher (2021) that high levels of professional development help principals provide tailored professional development opportunities for teachers and staff, enhancing their skills and abilities.

3.4. *School Climate*—In terms of school climate, Table 4 shows an extensive category mean rating of 3.57, which means that this domain of resource management ability of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte is oftentimes observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.87 to 3.84. The item the school heads for has programs or processes that help employees cope with incidents and prevent workplace accidents reflects a mean rating of 2.87, described as moderately ex-

tensive and interpreted as an item sometimes observed. Meanwhile, the item The facilities and physical condition of the organization I work for are ergonomic, comfortable, and appropriate shows a rating of 3.84, described as extensive and interpreted as an item oftentimes observed among school principals. This suggests that the prevailing atmosphere, culture, and social environment within the school is oftentimes observed in Talaingod, Davao del Norte. This finding supports the idea of Selamat et al. (2013) that a positive school climate promotes transparency in resource management. Principals with high levels of school climate foster an environment where stakeholders are well-informed about resource allocation and decisions. This supports the findings of Sherman (2018) that high school climate levels encourage collaborative resource management. Principals actively engage with teachers, staff, and other stakeholders to collectively optimize resources for the benefit of the school.

3.5. *Competency-Based Performance Appraisal*—The result in Table 5 shows that the resource management ability of school principals, in terms of competency-based performance appraisal, was assessed by the teachers as exten-

sive with a category mean of 3.62, interpreted as often observed in Talaingod, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.42 to 3.77. On one hand, the item, the school head, disseminates competency-based

Table 4. Resource Management Ability of School Principal in Terms of School Climate

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	The school head provides basic benefits.	3.59	Extensive
2	The school head has programs or processes that help employees cope with incidents and prevent workplace accidents.	2.87	Moderately Extensive
3	The school head is concerned with the safety of their employees by having access control of people who enter the company building/facilities.	3.59	Extensive
4	The school head provides additional benefits.	3.78	Extensive
5	The facilities and physical condition of the organization I work for are ergonomic, comfortable, and appropriate.	3.84	Extensive
6	The school head is concerned with my health and quality of life.	3.77	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.57	Extensive

performance appraisal criteria and results to its employees, which has a mean rating of 3.42, which is described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. On the other hand, the item Competency-based performance appraisal provides the basis for an employee development plan and reflects a mean of 3.77, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes observed.

Table 5. Resource Management Ability of School Principals in Terms of Competency-Based Performance Appraisal

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	The school head discusses competency-based performance appraisal criteria and results with its employees.	3.55	Extensive
2	Competency-based performance appraisal provides the basis for an employee development plan.	3.77	Extensive
3	Competency-based performance appraisal is the basis for decisions about promotions and salary increases.	3.76	Extensive
4	The school head disseminates competency-based performance appraisal criteria and results to its employees.	3.42	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.62	Extensive

This implies that the assessment process that evaluates the principal’s proficiency in key competencies and skills related to resource management within an educational institution is oftentimes observed in Talaingod, Davao del Norte. The result supports the findings of . This also supports the idea of Valentine et al. (2014) that high levels of competency-based performance appraisal ensure that school principals possess the essential skills and competencies for effective resource allocation and management. Principals are proficient in using data and evidence-based practices to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation. This is also congruent to the view of Hodges (2015) that competency-based appraisal promotes strate-

gic resource planning. Principals with high appraisal levels plan to align resource allocation with the school’s mission and long-term goals.

3.6. *Compensation and Rewards*—Specifically, examining the domain of compensation and rewards, results in Table 6 reveal that its category mean is 3.63, described as extensive, which means that this particular domain on resource management ability of school principals in Talaingod in Davao del Norte is oftentimes observed. The table further reveals that the

mean rating of the items ranges from 3.03 to 4.02. It is noteworthy that item, getting incentives such as promotions, commissioned functions, awards, bonuses, etc, has a mean rating of 3.03, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as item is sometimes observed while item, Being offered with a salary that is compatible with my skills, training, and education has a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed in Talaingod, Davao del Norte.

Table 6. Resource Management Ability of School Principal in Terms of Compensation and Rewards

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Getting incentives such as promotions, commissioned functions, awards, bonuses, etc.	3.03	Moderately Extensive
2	Knowing that my salary is influenced by my results.	3.89	Extensive
3	Being offered a salary that is compatible with my skills, training, and education.	4.02	Extensive
4	Being remunerated according to the remuneration offered at either the public or private marketplace levels.	3.75	Extensive
5	Considering the expectations and suggestions of its employees when designing a system of employee rewards.	3.48	Extensive
Mean		3.63	Extensive

This means that the assessment process that evaluates the principal’s proficiency in key competencies and skills related to resource management within an educational institution is oftentimes observed. The result agrees with the view of Valentine et al. (2014) that high levels of competency-based performance appraisal ensure that school principals possess the essential skills and competencies for effective resource allocation and management. Principals are proficient in using data and evidence-based practices to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation. This also supports the idea of Herlambang (2013) that high appraisal levels lead to resource optimization. Principals have the competencies to identify areas where resources

can be optimized and to implement innovative strategies for resource efficiency.

3.7. *Summarizes The Extent of School Principals’ Resource Management Ability in Talaingod, Davao del Norte*—Lastly, Table 7 summarizes the extent of school principals’ resource management ability in Talaingod, Davao del Norte. It shows that the overall mean resource management ability of school principals is 3.43, described as extensive. Moreover, the result indicates that the resource management ability of school principals in terms of compensation and rewards acquired the highest mean score of 3.63, which was described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed.

Table 7. Summary of Resource Management Ability of School Principal in Talaingod, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Workforce Management	2.96	Moderately Extensive
Collaboration	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Professional Development	3.46	Extensive
School Climate	3.57	Extensive
Competency-Based Performance Appraisal	3.62	Extensive
Compensation and Rewards	3.63	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

Meanwhile, school principals’ resource management ability in terms of work management got the lowest mean score of 2.96, which was described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed in Talaingod, Davao del Norte. This implies that principal’s capacity to effectively oversee and allocate various resources within the educational institution to support its mission and educational goals is oftentimes observed in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The result supports the idea of Dessler (2013) that principals with high levels of resource management ability can allocate resources strategically to support the school’s educational objectives and improve overall school performance. They use data and evidence-based practices to make informed decisions regarding resource allocation, ensuring that resources are directed where they would have the most impact. This also supports the view of Ellinger (2016) that high levels of resource management ability promote transparency and accountability

This suggests that the intentional efforts by school administrators and educational leaders to create an environment where collaboration is encouraged, supported, and recognized were oftentimes manifested. This finding supports the view of Döş and Savaş (2015) that school leaders ensure that the vision and mission of the school promote a collaborative culture among teachers, emphasizing common goals and objec-

in resource allocation. Principals ensure that resource management processes are transparent and well-documented.

3.8. *Teachers’ Cooperation in terms of Leadership and Governance*—In terms of leadership and governance, Table 8 shows an extensive category mean rating of 3.68, which means that this domain of teachers’ cooperation is oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.65 to 3.71. Using the Vision, Mission, and Goal (VMG) of DepEd as my guide in my participation in the development of school plans reflects a mean rating of 3.65, described as extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. Meanwhile, the item, Encouraging the team to regularly review the school plan to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges, and opportunities, show a rating of 3.71, described as extensive, interpreted as an item oftentimes manifested among the teachers.

tives. High levels of leadership and governance encourage shared decision-making. The result is also congruent with Orphanos’ (2013) idea that high levels of leadership and governance acknowledge and reward teachers who actively participate in cooperative activities, creating incentives for collaboration. Leaders establish processes for evaluating teachers’ cooperation and provide feedback to improve collaborative

Table 8. Teachers’ Cooperation in Terms of Leadership and Governance

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Contributing to the effort to develop the school plans.	3.70	Extensive
2	Using the Vision, Mission, and Goal (VMG) of DepEd as my guide in my participation in the development of school plans.	3.65	Extensive
3	Encouraging the team to regularly review the school plan to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.	3.71	Extensive
4	Perceiving that the school and community collaboratively define the organizational structure and responsibilities of stakeholders.	3.69	Extensive
5	Thinking that a network has been collaboratively established and is continuously improved by the school community.	3.69	Extensive
6	Contributing to the effort in addressing the training and development needs of the school and the community.	3.66	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.68	Extensive

efforts continuously.

3.9. *Curriculum and Instruction*—Table 9 shows that the teachers in Talaingod District assessed teachers’ cooperation in terms of cur-

riculum and instruction as extensive, with a category mean of 3.69, interpreted as frequently manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.63 to 3.77.

On the one hand, the item, Encouraging the administration and other external stakeholders to ensure that the creative thinking and problem-solving skills of the learners are developed, has a mean rating of 3.63, described as extensive, interpreted as item sometimes manifested. On the other hand, the item Taking responsibility in ensuring that the learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community reflects a mean of 3.77, described as extensive, interpreted as oftentimes manifested. This means that the incorporation of collaborative elements into the curriculum and teaching methodologies, as well as the alignment of instructional practices with the goal of fostering high levels of cooperation among teaching staff within an educational institution, is oftentimes manifested in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The result supports Tang et al.’s (2012) idea that curriculum de-

signs incorporate interdisciplinary projects that require teachers from different subjects to work together, promoting cross-disciplinary cooperation. The curriculum includes instructional strategies that encourage teachers to work collaboratively in designing and delivering lessons, fostering high levels of cooperation. This is also congruent with McShane and Von Glinow (2012) view that instruction and curriculum emphasize inclusive teaching practices involving collaboration among teachers to support students with diverse needs and abilities.

3.10. *Accountability and Continuous Improvement*—Table 10 shows that the teachers in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte assessed the domain of accountability and continuous improvement as extensive, with a category mean of 3.67, interpreted as often observed. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.58 to 3.75.

Table 9. Teachers’ Cooperation in Terms of Curriculum and Instruction

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Being involved in ensuring that the curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of learners in the school community.	3.73	Extensive
2	Helping the school in ensuring that programs are fully implemented and closely monitored to address performance discrepancies, benchmark best practices, coach low performers, mentor potential leaders, reward high achievement, and maintain an environment that makes learning meaningful and enjoyable.	3.75	Extensive
3	Making sure that the implemented curriculum is localized to make it meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	3.70	Extensive
4	Encouraging the administration and other external stakeholders to ensure that the creative thinking and problem-solving skills of the learners are developed.	3.63	Extensive
5	Taking responsibility in ensuring that the learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community.	3.77	Extensive
6	Taking part in ensuring that appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved, and assessment results are contextualized to the learners and local situation in the attainment of relevant life skills.	3.64	Extensive
7	Ensuring that the teachers, administrators, and community members nurture values and environments that are protective of all children and demonstrate behavior consistent with the organization’s vision, mission, and goals.	3.66	Extensive
8	I make sure that methods and resources are learners and community-friendly.	3.71	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.69	Extensive

On the one hand, the item Taking part in developing and deciding on the accountability assessment criteria tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes has a mean rating of 3.58, described as moderately extensive, interpreted as an item sometimes manifested. On the other hand, the item Helping in defining and setting roles as well as responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies reflects a mean of 3.75 described as extensive, interpreted as oftentimes manifested. This means that the establishment of a system of accountability and continuous improvement processes that promote

and enhance a culture of collaboration and cooperation among teachers is oftentimes manifested. This supports Shukla’s (2014) idea that high levels of accountability and continuous improvement emphasize shared responsibility among teachers for collaborating effectively and achieving common goals. Schools set specific goals and expectations for collaborative activities, ensuring that teachers are held accountable for working together to meet these goals. This is similar to Albdour and Altarawneh’s (2014) assertion that accountability processes ensure that collaborative efforts align with the school’s goals and mission, keeping the focus on the

Table 10. Teachers’ Cooperation in Terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Helping in defining and setting roles as well as responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies.	3.75	Extensive
2	Recognizing the achievement of goals based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system can help address gaps through appropriate action.	3.70	Extensive
3	Helping in the enhancement of the accountability system to ensure that the management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the merging learning needs and demands of the community.	3.71	Extensive
4	Taking part in developing and deciding on the accountability assessment criteria tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes.	3.58	Extensive
5	Participating in the school-initiated periodic assessment and shared feedback.	3.59	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.67	Extensive

institution’s educational objectives.

3.11. *Management of Resources*—Specifically, examining the domain of management of resources, results in Table 11 reveal that its category mean is 3.68, described as exten-

sive, which means that this particular domain on teachers’ cooperation is oftentimes manifested. The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 3.61 to 3.71.

Table 11. Teachers’ Cooperation in Terms of Management of Resources

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Participating in resource inventory, which serves as the basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	3.71	Extensive
2	Engaging in regular dialogues for planning and resource programming, and support the implementation of community education plans.	3.61	Extensive
3	Helping ensure that there is a community developed resource management system towards judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	3.70	Extensive
4	Participating in the monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management.	3.68	Extensive
5	Helping to manage and sustain an established system of partnership with external stakeholders.	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.68	Extensive

It is noteworthy that item, Engaging in regular dialogues for planning and resource programming, and support the implementation of community education plans has a mean rating of

3.61, described as extensive, interpreted as item is often manifested, while item, Participating in resource inventory which serves as the basis for resource allocation and mobilization has

a mean rating of 3.71, described as extensive and interpreted as item often manifested. The result implies that the strategic allocation, utilization, and facilitation of resources within an educational institution to support and enhance a culture of collaboration and cooperation among teachers is often manifested in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. This finding supports Bucud’s (2017) view that efficient resource management ensures that teachers have the necessary resources to collaborate effectively, which is essential for improving teaching and learning. Resource allocation for professional development opportunities on cooperation and collaboration can enhance teachers’ skills and strategies for effective teamwork.

3.12. *Summarizes The Extent of Teachers’ Cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte*—Lastly, Table 12 summarizes the extent of teachers’ cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The table shows that teachers’ cooperation obtained an overall mean score of 3.68, descriptively rated as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested. Moreover, the result showed that teachers’ cooperation in curriculum and instruction acquired the highest mean score of 3.69, which was described as ex-

tensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. Meanwhile, teachers’ cooperation in terms of accountability and continuous improvement got the lowest mean score of 3.67, which was described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested by the teachers in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. This indicates a strong spirit of collaboration and teamwork among educators in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. The finding is congruent with Oswald’s (2014) discussion that teachers who cooperate at a high level can collaboratively plan lessons and teaching strategies, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards and optimizing student learning experience. High levels of cooperation facilitate shared professional development opportunities. Teachers can learn from one another and build on each other’s expertise. This supports the idea of Khattri et al. (2010) that high levels of cooperation support a culture of continuous improvement. Teachers engage in reflective practices and adapt their teaching methods based on feedback and results. Teachers cooperate to share responsibility for achieving educational goals and ensuring students meet academic standards.

Table 12. Summary of Teachers’ Cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Leadership and Governance	3.68	Extensive
Curriculum and Instruction	3.69	Extensive
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.67	Extensive
Management of Resources	3.68	Extensive
Overall Mean	3.68	Extensive

3.13. *Structural Supervision of School Principals*—Results in Table 13 reveal that the structural supervision of the school principal in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte acquired a mean score of 3.27, described as moderately extensive. This means that structural supervision of school principals is sometimes evident.

The table further reveals that the mean rating of the items ranges from 2.95 to 3.56. It is noteworthy that the item Setting specific, measurable goals and hold people accountable for results has a mean rating of 2.95, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as an item that is sometimes manifested, while the item Empha-

sizing careful planning and clear timelines has a mean rating of 3.56, described as extensive and interpreted as item oftentimes manifested.

Table 13. Structural Supervision of School Principals in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1	Thinking clearly and logically.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
2	Emphasizing careful planning and clear timelines.	3.56	Extensive
3	Approaching problems through logical analysis and careful thinking.	3.29	Moderately Extensive
4	Develop and implement clear, logical policies and procedures.	3.44	Extensive
5	Approaching problems with facts and logic.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
6	Setting specific, measurable goals and holding people accountable for results.	2.95	Moderately Extensive
7	Having extraordinary attention to detail.	3.25	Moderately Extensive
8	Believing in a clear structure and a chain of command.	3.54	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.27	Moderately Extensive

The result implies that the performance and activities of school principals are systematically monitored and assessed based on predefined criteria, guidelines, and organizational structures, which is sometimes evident in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte. This finding supports the view of Sergiovanni (2013) that moderate structural supervision holds school principals accountable for their administrative and leadership roles. It ensures that they are fulfilling their duties and responsibilities. Moreover, the result is similar to Day et al.'s (2011) view that structural supervision holds school principals accountable for their leadership and administrative roles, ensuring they meet the established standards and expectations. It serves as a quality assurance mechanism to maintain and enhance the quality of education in schools. By monitoring principals' performance, it helps ensure that schools are led effectively.

3.14. *Relationship among Resource Management Ability of School Principals, Teachers' Cooperation, Structural Supervision in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte*—The analysis

of the relationship among school principals' resource management ability, teachers' cooperation, and structural supervision in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product-moment correlation was used to determine the relationship among the mentioned variables. Meanwhile, Table 14 shows that the resource management ability of school principals has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .772, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of the resource management ability of school principals, teachers' cooperation also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. This is congruent with Ambali et al.'s (2011) proposition that principals adept at resource management can allocate resources effectively. This

includes budgetary resources for instructional materials, professional development, support staff, and physical resources like classrooms and technology. They can provide teachers with opportunities for professional development, workshops, and training, which enhances their teaching skills and motivation. On the one hand, the result shows that the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and structural supervision in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte has a significant positive relationship with a p-value of .00 that is less than alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.692$ $p < 0.05$). This means that if the extent of resource management ability of school principals changes, the extent of structural supervision also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and structural supervision in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. This result corroborates with Oumer and Kejela's (2017) conclusion that effective structural supervision can enhance the impact of resource management by ensuring that the resources allocated are used efficiently. It can also ensure that teachers are accountable for their use of

resources. More so, principals who excel in resource management are likely to have strong communication and collaboration skills. They can foster an environment where teachers feel heard and supported. On the other hand, the result shows that the relationship between structural supervision has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .00 that is less than the alpha set at .05 ($r = 0.684$ $p < .05$). This means that if the extent of structural supervision changes, teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte also significantly changes. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between structural supervision and a significant positive relationship between the teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. This is congruent with the view of Kurland et al. (2010) that structural supervision may involve input from various stakeholders, including teachers, staff, parents, and community members, ensuring a more comprehensive evaluation. Mechanisms for resolving conflicts and disputes related to the supervision process are often established, promoting staff collaboration.

Table 14. Relationship among Resource Management Ability of School Principals, Teachers' Cooperation, Structural Supervision in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte

Variables	Teachers' Cooperation	Structural Supervision
Resource Management Ability of School Principals	0.772**	0.692**
Teachers' Cooperation	1	0.684**
	0.000	0.000

**Significant @ $p < 0.05$

3.15. *The Mediating Effect of Structural Supervision on the Relationship Between Resource Management Ability of School Principals and Teachers' Cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte*—The mediating effect of structural supervision (SS) on the rela-

pals and Teachers' Cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte—The mediating effect of structural supervision (SS) on the rela-

tionship between resource management ability (RMA) of school principals and teachers' cooperation (TC) in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte was tested using the Sobel z-Test. Results Table 14 shows that the total effect of resource management ability (RMA) of school principals as the independent variable on the teachers' cooperation (TC), which is this study's dependent variable, is significant, as evident in the estimated value of 0.977 and $p < 0.05$. On the one hand, it could be seen in the table that the direct effect of resource management ability (RMA) of school principals on the teachers' cooperation (TC) is significant, as indicated by an estimated value of 0.124, $p < 0.05$. Lastly, the resource man

agement ability (RMA) of school principals on the teachers' cooperation (TC) with structural supervision (SS) as a mediator is significant, as indicated by the estimated value of 0.468 and $p < 0.05$. This means that structural supervision (SS) partially mediated the relationship between the resource management ability (RMA) of school principals and the moral work behavior (MWB) of teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis of structural supervision (SS) does not mediate the relationship between resource management ability (RMA) of school principals and teachers' cooperation (TC) in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte is rejected.

Table 15. The Mediating Effect of Structural Supervision on the Relationship Between Resource Management Ability of School Principals and Teachers' Cooperation in Talaingod District, Davao del Norte

Effect Type	Path	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
Indirect Effect Components	RMA → SS → TC	0.468	0.076	6.186	0.000
Direct Effect	RMA → TC	0.124	0.052	2.390	0.000
Total Effect	RMA → TC	0.977	0.124	7.856	0.000

Mediating Size = 0.4790

Legend: RMA=Resource Management Ability; TC=Teachers' Cooperation; SS=Structural Supervision

The table also indicates the results of the computation of the effect size in the mediation test conducted between the three variables. The effect size measures how much of the effect of school principals' resource management ability (RMA) on the teachers' cooperation (TC) in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte can be attributed to the indirect path. As shown in the figure, the mediating size obtains a value of 0.4790, indicating that about 47.90 percent of the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 52.10 percent of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other vari-

ables not included in the model. Through mediation analysis, the mediation model shown in Figure 2 was generated. The significant role of structural supervision (SS) as a mediator in the relationship between the resource management ability (RMA) of school principals and teachers' cooperation (TC) in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte is contributed by the fact that there exists a relationship among these variables. It is emphasized in this study that structural supervision (SS) is an undeniable factor that has a positive relationship between the resource management ability (RMA) of school principals and teachers' cooperation (TC) in Talaingod Dis-

Fig. 2. Mediation Model

strict in Davao del Norte. The result implies that effective structural supervision can serve as a catalyst for improved teacher cooperation. It creates an environment where teachers are more inclined to work together, share resources, and collaborate on instructional strategies. This supports the findings of Heisenberg and Heilbrunner (2011) that the resource management ability of a school principal plays a pivotal role

in fostering teachers' cooperation. Structural supervision complements this by providing the necessary structure, accountability, and support to maximize the positive impact of resource management on teacher collaboration. When these elements work in tandem, they can create a conducive environment for enhanced cooperation and the overall success of the school.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussions were supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusions were based on the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the mediating effect of structural supervision on the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive-predictive technique. The researcher selected the 200 elementary

school teachers in Talaingod District, Division of Davao del Norte, as the respondents through a stratified random sampling method. The researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Based on the results, the summary of

the findings was the following: The resource management ability of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte acquired an overall mean of 3.43 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, the resource management ability of school principals in terms of workforce management, collaboration, professional development, school climate, competency-based performance appraisal, and compensation and rewards obtained mean scores of 2.96, 3.31, 3.46, 3.57, 3.62, and 3.63, respectively. Teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.68 and a descriptive rating of extensive. Also, teachers' cooperation in leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and resource management obtained mean scores of 3.68, 3.69, 3.67, and 3.68, respectively. More so, the structural supervision of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte was rated moderately extensive, with an overall mean score of 3.27. The result showed that the resource management ability of school principals has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' cooperation in structural supervision in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .772, p < 0.05$), and ($r = .692, p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, structural supervision has a significant positive relationship with the teachers' cooperation in structural supervision in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .684, p < 0.05$). Structural supervision partially mediates the relationship between the resource management ability of school principals and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. The analysis obtained the estimated value of 0.468 with $p < 0.05$, 0.124 with $p < 0.05$, and 0.977 with $p < 0.05$ for indirect, direct, and total effects, respectively. Moreover, the ratio index (mediating size) obtained a value of 0.479, indicating that about 47.90 percent of

the total effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable goes through the mediator variable, and about 52.10 percent of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The resource management ability of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte was rated as extensive. The extent of the resource management ability of school principals in terms of professional development, school climate, competency-based performance appraisal, and compensation and rewards obtained an extensive descriptive rating. Meanwhile, the resource management ability of school principals in terms of workforce management and collaboration acquired a moderate extensive rating. The result suggests that principal's capacity to effectively oversee and allocate various resources within the educational institution to support its mission and educational goals is oftentimes observed. Teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte was extensive. Meanwhile, teachers' cooperation in leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources belong to extensive rating. This implies a strong spirit of collaboration and teamwork among educators. Structural supervision of school principals in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte was described as moderately extensive. The result implies that the performance and activities of school principals were systematically monitored and assessed based on predefined criteria, guidelines, and organizational structures is sometimes evident. The resource management ability of school principals has a positive significant relationship with structural supervision and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. Also, structural supervision has a positive significant relationship with teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao

del Norte. Structural supervision partially mediates the relationship between school principals' resource management ability and teachers' cooperation in Talaingod District in Davao del Norte. Effective structural supervision can catalyze improved teacher cooperation. It creates an environment where teachers are more inclined to collaborate, share resources, and collaborate on instructional strategies.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions generated from the study, the researcher recommends the following: The Department of Education may ensure that schools receive adequate resources to support classroom instruction and structural supervision. Adequate funding is critical for effective resource management. In addition, DepEd should implement mechanisms to monitor and assess the effectiveness of school principals in resource management and structural supervision. This data can inform policy decisions and accountability measures. School principals

may continuously work on enhancing their leadership skills, including resource management and supervision techniques. They should seek out professional development opportunities and mentorship. They should align resource allocation decisions with the school's goals and the needs of teachers and students. They should prioritize resources that support teaching and learning. Teachers may support leadership initiatives aimed at enhancing resource management and structural supervision. Participation and engagement in these efforts can lead to more effective cooperation. They should actively collaborate with colleagues, share resources and ideas, and work together to address common goals and challenges. Future researchers may conduct research in diverse educational settings to understand better how the relationships between resource management, structural supervision, and teacher cooperation may vary across different contexts.

5. References

- Abdulla Al Kaabi, S. A. (2015). An evaluation of the school-based management practices in the new school model: A study on al ain schools [Retrieved from https://scholarworks.uaeu.ac.ae/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1037&context=all_theses].
- Abulencia, A. A. (2013). *School-based management: A structural reform intervention* [Retrieved from <http://goo.gl/MBBtnp>]. Center for linkages; extension, Philippine Normal University.
- Allawan, F. D. (2012). School's community partnership practices and stakeholders' involvement in digos city division [Unpublished Master's Thesis, Southern Philippines AgriBusiness and Marine and Aquatic School of Technology, Mati, Digos City].
- Arar, K., & Abo-Rome, A. (2016). School-based management: Arab education system in israel [Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1096039>]. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 54(2), 191–208.
- Armstrong, M., & Brown, D. (2019). Strategic human resource management: Back to the future? [Retrieved from https://www.employmentstudies.co.uk/system/files/resources/files/517_Strategic-Human-Resource-Management-Back-to-the-future-IES-CIPD-2019.pdf].
- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2014). *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice*. Kogan Page.
- Baker, E. (2015). Exploring meanings of professional development: Teacher perspectives [Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/62779978.pdf>].

- Bandy, J. (2020). Learning to apply knowledge and skills to benefit others or serve the public good [Retrieved from <https://www.ideaedu.org/idea-notes-on-learning/learning-to-apply-knowledge-and-skills-to-benefit-others-or-serve-the-public-good/>].
- Barasa, T. (2014). *Successful decentralization: The roles and challenges of deos in kenya*. The International Institute for Educational Planning (IIEP).
- Barrera-Osorio, F., Fasih, T., Patrinos, H. A., & Santibáñez, L. (2014). Decentralized decision-making in schools: The theory and evidence on school-based management [Retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/227831468169753582/Decentralized-decision-making-in-schools-the-theory-and-evidence-on-school-based-management>].
- Bogatova, M. (2017). Improving recruitment, selection and retention of employees. case: Dpoint-group ltd [Retrieved from https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/123598/Maria_Bogatova_Thesis.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y].
- Boudreaux, M. K., Martin, R., & McNeal, L. (2016). Perceptions of quality school facilities – implications for the school administrator [Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/irhe.v1n2p164>]. *International Research in Higher Education*, 1(2), 164–174.
- Buchan, J., Twigg, D., Dussault, G., Duffield, C., & Stone, P. W. (2016). Policies to sustain the nursing workforce: An international perspective. *International Nurse Review*, 62(2), 162–170.
- Bucud, R. (2017). The effects decentralization on community participation in school-based management in the philippines [Retrieved from <https://researchbank.rmit.edu.au/eserv/rmit:162390/Bucud.pdf>].
- Cabardo, J. R. (2016). Levels of participation of the school stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities and the implementation of school-based management [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1133596.pdf>]. *Journal of Inquiry & Action in Education*, 8(1), 81–94.
- Chege, A. W. (2016). The influence of employee benefits on retention at safaricom limited [Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya].
- Choudhary, N., & Lamba, S. (2013). Impact of hrm practices on organizational commitment of employees [Retrieved from <http://www.ijoart.org/docs/IMPACT-OF-HRM-PRACTICES-ON-ORGANIZATIONAL-COMMITMENT-OF-EMPLOYEES.pdf>]. *International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology*, 2(4), 407–422.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Demo, G., Neiva, E. R., Nunes, I., & Rozzett, K. (2012). Human resources management policies and practices scale (hrmpss): Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis [Retrieved from <http://www.anpad.org.br/bar>]. *Brasilia Administration Review*.
- Dessler, G. (2013). *Human resource management*. Pearson Education.
- Dufflo, E., Dupas, P., & Kremer, M. (2015). School governance, teacher incentives, and pupil–teacher ratios: Experimental evidence from kenyan primary schools [Retrieved from https://web.stanford.edu/~pdupas/DDK_ETP.pdf].
- Dzimiri, W., & Marimo, S. T. (2015). Challenges faced in the implementation of the zimbabwe localized advanced level geography syllabus: A case of gweru district high schools [Retrieved from <http://ir.msu.ac.zw:8080/xmlui/handle/11408/1547?show=full>]. *Global Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 4(2), 52–56.

- Ellinger, A. D. (2016). Contextual factors influencing informal learning in a workplace setting: The case of reinventing itself company [Retrieved from https://www.ufhrd.co.uk/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2010/08/3_4.pdf]. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 16(3), 389–415.
- Gerhart, B. (2015). Research on human resources and effectiveness: Some methodological challenges. In J. Paauwe, D. E. Guest, & P. M. Wright (Eds.), *Hrm and performance* (pp. 149–171). Wiley.
- Gould-Sandy, J. (2013). The importance of hr practices and workplace trust in achieving superior performance: A study of public-sector organizations [Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09585190210158501>]. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 14(1), 28–54.
- Hilaire, A., & Kosinski, M. (2015). Your recruiters are your employer brand: Why it matters who does your recruiting [Retrieved from <https://www.recruiter.com/downloads/your-recruiters-are-your-employer-brand-why-it-matters-who-does-your-recruiting>].
- Hough, H. J. (2014). Salary incentives and teacher quality: The effect of a district-level salary increase on teacher recruitment [Retrieved from <https://cepa.stanford.edu/content/research-brief-the-effect-of-a-district-level-salary-increase-on-teacher-recruitment>].
- Hubschmid, E. (2013). *Shaping efficient employer branding strategies to target generation y: A cross-national perspective on recruitment marketing* [Retrieved from <https://www.peterlang.com/document/1052885>]. Peter Lang AG.
- Joynes, C., Rossignoli, S., & Amonoo-Kuofi, E. F. (2019). 21st century skills: Evidence of issues in definition, demand and delivery for development contexts [Retrieved from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5d71187ce5274a097c07b985/21st_century.pdf].
- Kaabi, A. A., & Ali, S. (2015). An evaluation of the school-based management practices in the new school model: A study on al ain schools [Masters' thesis, United Arab Emirates University, Retrieved from <https://docplayer.net/60005985-An-evaluationof-the-school-based-management-practices-in-the-new-schoolmodel-a-study-on-al-ain-schools.html>].
- Khattri, N., Ling, C., & Jha, C. (2013). The effects of school-based management in the philippines: An initial assessment using administrative data [Retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/264231468093865092/The-effects-of-school-based-management-in-the-Philippines-an-initial-assessment-using-administrative-data>].
- Kossivi, B., Xu, M., & Kalgora, B. (2016). Study on determining factors of employee retention [Retrieved from https://file.scirp.org/pdf/JSS_2016053009190527.pdf]. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(5), 261–273.
- Lim, W. M. (2012). Organisational strategic human resource management – the case of lehman brothers [Retrieved from <http://10.5296/jmr.v4i2.1368>]. *Journal of Management Research*, 4(2), 1–8.
- Lindberg, E., & Vanyushyn, V. (2014). School-based management with or without instructional leadership: Experience from sweden [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1077175.pdf>]. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 2(3), 39–50.
- Marler, J. H., & Boudreau, J. W. (2017). An evidence-based review of hr analytics [Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09585192.2016.1244699>]. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 28(1), 3–26.

- Monaco, T. (2016). Improving the recruitment and retention of teachers in rural rwanda [Retrieved from <https://dukespace.lib.duke.edu>].
- Moradi, S., Bin Hussin, S., & Barzegar, N. (2012). School-based management (sbm), opportunity or threat (education systems of iran) [International Conference on Education and Educational Psychology (ICEEPSY 2012), Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/82226064.pdf>].
- Ndung'u, V. (2014). An investigation into the influence of culture on employability and work ethic, and the role of tertiary educators on graduates preparedness in botswana [Retrieved from <https://eujournal.org/index.php/esj/article/viewFile/4013/3824>].
- of Education, D. (2012). Implementing guidelines on the revised school-based management (sbm) framework, assessment process and tool (apat) [In DepEd Order No. 83, s. 2012. DepEd Complex, Meralco Avenue, Pasig City].
- Oswald, L. J. (2014). School-based management: Rationale and implementation guidelines paperback [Retrieved from <https://www.amazon.com/SchoolBased-Management-Rationale-Implementation-Guidelines/dp/1502513161>].
- Pañares, N. C., & Palmes, N. (2014). School-based management implementation in the school divisions of misamis oriental: An assessment for policy recommendation [Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318468607>].
- Passarelli, A. M. (2016). Vision-based coaching: Optimizing resources for leader development [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00412>]. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6(412), 1–15.
- Shashi, S. (2014). Teaching competency, professional commitment and job satisfaction-a study of primary school teachers [Retrieved from www.iosrjournals.org]. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 4(3), 44–64.
- Shaukat, H., Ashraf, N., & Ghafoor, S. (2015). Impact of human resource management practices on employees performance [Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/35295637/Impact_of_Human_Resource_Management_Practices_on_Employees_Performance]. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 23(2), 329–338.
- Tabouli, E. M. A., Habtoor, N. A., & Nashiefs, M. (2016). Human resources management policies and practices scale (hrmpps): Using confirmatory factor analysis (cfa) [Retrieved from https://www.worldresearchlibrary.org/up_proc/pdf/341-14672135863-8.pdf].
- Tansiri, I. Y., & Bong, Y. J. (2018). The analysis of school-based management (sbm) implementation to the educational quality service of state junior high school [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2991/icream-18.2019.89>]. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*, 258, 424–426.
- Tety, J. L. (2016). The role of instructional materials in academic performance in community secondary schools in rombo district [Retrieved from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/83632862.pdf>].
- Tiwari, P., & Saxena, K. (2012). Human resource management practices: A comprehensive review [Retrieved from https://pbr.iobm.edu.pk/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/120103_HRM-Practices-Tiwari-37.pdf]. *Pakistan Business Review*, 669–705.
- Usman, Y. D. (2016). Educational resources: An integral component for effective school administration in nigeria [Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED578024.pdf>]. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(13), 27–37.

- Vally, G. V. S., & Daud, K. (2015). The implementation of school based management policy: An exploration [Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042815004589>]. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 172, 693–700.
- VanMeter, R. A., Grisaffe, D. B., Chonko, L. B., & Roberts, J. A. (2014). Generation y's ethical ideology and its potential workplace implications [Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/42001969>]. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 117, 93–109.
- Varatharaj, R., Abdullah, A. G. K., & Ismail, A. (2015). The effect of teacher autonomy on assessment practices among malaysian cluster school teachers [Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.1/2015.5.1/1.1.31.36>]. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 5(1), 31–36.
- Vernez, G., Karam, R., & Marshall, J. H. (2012). Implementation of school-based management in indonesia [The RAND Corporation, Santa Monica, CA. Retrieved from https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/monographs/2012/RAND_MG1229.sum.pdf].
- Vijayabanu, C. (2017). Perceived organization climate and work commitment in indian private manufacturing sector [Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321666554_Perceived_organization_climate_and_work_commitment_in_indian_private_manufacturing_sector]. *International Journal of Economic Research*, 14(8), 1–12.
- Vincent, S., & Joseph, A. (2015). Challenges for human resource experts in global scenario. *International Journal of advancement in Research and Technology*, 2(4), 209–214.
- Zajda, J. I., & Gamage, D. T. (2014). Decentralisation, school-based management and quality [Retrieved from <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9789048127023>].